

DEVELOPMENT FACTORS OF "ECOLOGICAL
MANAGEMENT" IN THE CONDITIONS OF GREEN ECONOMY IN
UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *This article talks about the importance, role and ways of "ecological management" in the context of green economy development in Uzbekistan. At the moment, the "green" economy is developing all over the world, the "green" economy is closely interconnected with the environment and the circular economy, which implies a rejection of the traditional linear model of economic development.*

Keywords. *Management, green economy, economy, development, environment, economic activity, business management.*

In conditions of a sharp deterioration of the environmental situation, fundamental changes are taking place in the theory and practice of enterprise management. A key factor driving these changes is the realization that environmental problems pose a major challenge to life on the planet and require immediate action. In this context, enterprise management becomes an important tool in addressing environmental issues that are affected by economic activities.

Environmental management is an important aspect of business management today. It is based on the ideas of environmental responsibility and sustainable development, and also means managing a business with the

environment in mind. This means that companies must take care of their environmental performance and allow it to influence their work process.

The goals of environmental management include reducing the negative impact of businesses on the environment, increasing resource efficiency, and raising certain environmental standards, which can enhance a company's reputation. This is all achieved through the use of various technologies and management methods, such as environmental auditing, environmental design and modern resource management solutions.

At the moment, the “green” economy is developing all over the world, the “green” economy is closely interconnected with the environment and the circular economy, which implies a rejection of the traditional linear model of economic development. Environmental management is built on the basis of these industries.

Environmental management is a management mechanism that creates environmental safety at enterprises and ensures a normal relationship between the environmental and financial performance of the enterprise, which affects the performance of the enterprise itself. It is important to understand the need for interaction between production development management and environmental process management.

Today, ecology provides new guidelines for the development of further production paths; environmental management, in turn, is aimed at expanding environmentally friendly technologies and introducing innovations into production activities. This system also includes the principles of the “green” economy. It represents tools that influence people's well-being and reduce the risks of negative impacts on the environment. The reason for the difficult environmental situation at enterprises is the lack of management in production, as well as weak control by the state, which is responsible for the environment.

In accordance with this, a system of environmental management methods has been developed that will provide environmental control at three levels:

1. Organizational – maintaining the organizational culture of the enterprise.
2. National – providing support from the state apparatus.
3. International – formation of international environmental policy and improvement of international trade conditions.

There are currently four principles of a green economy:

❖ the principle of sustainability, which represents society's recognition of the limited resources: it is necessary to use them carefully and look for ways to restore them, therefore the economy should not go beyond the ecological framework and at the same time provide opportunities for development;

❖ the principle of justice and dignity states that the environment must be treated with care so that the high quality of the environment is preserved for future generations;

❖ the principle of management and flexibility – economic activity must comply with general environmental standards and bear responsibility for the damage caused;

❖ the principle of a healthy planet, which represents investment in nature by the state, support and restoration of the environment on its part.

To implement the principles, the state must comply with the stages of the “green” economy. Each of these stages makes its contribution to the development of the enterprise, and also fills the country's economy. To fully contribute to the economy, you need to follow the following actions:

✓ reduction of cash payments for harmful substances by introducing sanctions to redistribute payments to improve the environmental environment;

✓ attracting additional investment for the development of agriculture, water supply and new energy sources;

✓ increase in fines for environmental protection zones.

As part of this, environmental management can be organized by “green technologies” - changing the basis of production to the use of renewable energy

sources, outdated technologies and waste disposal processes. Industrial waste management is the activity of collection, accumulation, transportation, processing, disposal, neutralization, disposal of waste, conditions and methods of disposal. So, in our country, companies can store them in specially designated landfills, burn them or pre-sort them and dispose of them into secondary raw materials.

The impact of this is positive not only in relation to the environment, but also for enterprises - it can help increase the company's productivity and its competitiveness in the market, and improve its reputation among consumers. Within the framework of the “green” economy, environmental management can also be implemented through green finance, which is smart taxation to control the harmful effects on nature and foster positive environmental habits, as well as investing in environmental projects.

Environmental management involves the individual collection and analysis of data on environmental indicators such as resource consumption and pollutant emissions. This allows companies to identify where their processes can be improved and which resources can be used less to reduce their environmental impact. Overall, environmental management is important for the implementation of economic activities nowadays, as this concept helps to increase the company's productivity and its experience in the field of environmental responsibility. It also helps reduce resource costs, which results in increased profits for the company.

In general, companies that take environmental management into account can increase their competitiveness in the market, improve their reputation among consumers and the public, and improve living conditions on the planet as a whole.

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